

MAHMUDKHOJA BEHBUDIY AS THE FOUNDER OF THE UZBEK NATIONAL SCHOOL OF JADIDISM

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Annotation: *This article highlights the turning points in the life of Mahmudhoja Behbudi, his hard work due to some fanatical and tsarist government, his attention to the education of young people and his invaluable services in this direction. prohibited*

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The son of the people of Samarkand, one of the active leaders of the Jadid movement, playwright, great writer, publicist, religious and public figure Mahmudkhoja Behbudi made a significant contribution to the development of schools, education and theater in XIX century Turkestan. At the same time, he became the father of the Uzbek national Jadidism. The atmosphere in the family of intellectuals led to his interest in literature, politics and enlightenment.

In addition to the Russian, Turkish, and Iranian revolutions, the Crimean and Volga Tatar press, especially Ismailbek Gasprinsky's Tarjimon newspaper, played an important role in the spread of the Jadid movement in Turkestan in the early twentieth century. Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, a leading enlightened writer of his time, who felt that the press was a powerful weapon in the hands of progressives, began publishing the newspaper "Turkistan Region", "Taraqiy", "Khurshid", "Shuhrat", "Osiyo", "Tujjor" in 1901. He has published more than 200 articles in local newspapers and magazines.

He tried to open people's eyes with these articles. At the same time, he opened the first Jadid schools in Samarkand and began to create manuals and textbooks for them. Behbudi, together with Abdulkadir Shakuri, opened the first school of the new method in the village of Rajabamin in 1903, and then in 1906 moved it to the courtyard of the city and adopted him as his father. In the same years he published "Muntahabi Geography" ("Brief General Geography"), "Madhali Geography of Russia" ("Brief Geography of Russia"), "Kitabat ul-Atfol" ("Children's Book"), He created textbooks and manuals such as "A Brief History of Islam" ("A Brief History of Islam") and "Practice of Islam". These works alone testify to the fact that Behbudi was a scholar with a thorough knowledge of both religious and secular knowledge.

The people who brought geniuses such as Beruni and Al-Khwarizmi, Ibn Sino and Al-Farghani, Ulugbek and Navoi to world science and culture came to the middle of the 19th century for various objective reasons. had become one of the backward nations. That is why Behbudi devoted all his energy and zeal to the enlightenment of this people, not only as a publicist and educator, but also as a skilful organizer and herald of the ideas of the new historical epoch.

Enlightenment activities are not limited to schools. Realizing this fact, Behbudi in 1908 in Samarkand founded one of the first modern libraries in Turkestan - the "Reading House of Islam". Later, called the Library of Behbudiya, this center of enlightenment functioned until 1919 and played a role in the formation of religious and secular knowledge of the youth of Samarkand. With a capacity of up to 11 readers a day, the library soon became one of Samarkand's largest educational institutions, gradually accumulating more than 1,000 unique books. In addition to various textbooks and manuals, the Behbudi publishing house has published a map of Turkestan, Bukhara and Khiva. The restless man, seeing that his ideas and views did not reach the masses, found it necessary to create a national theater for those who were illiterate or deprived of the rays of enlightenment due to their short stature. In 1911 he wrote the play "Padarkush" for the Uzbek theater.

The activities of the Uzbek Jadids, led by Behbudi, aimed at enlightening the people, were strongly opposed by Tsarist Russia on the one hand, and the Emirate of Bukhara on the other. The Emir, who considered the Jadids to be his worst enemy, and his fanatical siege, wherever he saw a Jadid, killed him and declared him a disbeliever. , it ignited unhealthy feelings.

After Friday prayers in the mosque of the Ulugbek Madrasah in Samarkand on January 3, 1914, the muezzin addressed five or six thousand Muslims and said, If he gives, he will be a disbeliever and his wife will be divorced. The takfir, proclaimed by the cleric, spread like wildfire throughout Turkestan, and the Jadids found themselves in a difficult situation.

In such a difficult situation, wise and virtuous Jadids, such as Behbudi, were required to protect their Jadid schools and their teachers with the help of religious evidence. Mufti Behbudi honorably fulfilled this responsibility and forced the cleric to deny himself takfir, that is, he declared the Jadids to be infidels. In such a difficult situation, Behbudi did not stop for a moment, his enthusiasm increased, but he did not give up. We have a class of respectable young people in Turkestan and Bukhara who work in government courts as secretaries, translators, salesmen and brokers, and there are thousands of them in Bukhara and Turkestan today. The appeal to these young people is to say a few words to our countrymen, even from this class. Please listen to us. And with all due respect, we would like to inform you that most of you have been able to read and write a little bit of Russian, or just speak, to the best of your ability. you will live a life of ease and a little prosperity, taking on the task of a little modern knowledge, so that my Tanfim may increase! And the fact that you know a little bit of modern knowledge has certainly benefited

you, and, thank God, you are also a good believer in religion, and this knowledge has not broken your modern beliefs. After all, Islam is such a strong and capable religion that the more knowledge one reads, the stronger one's faith in Islam will be. For example, it is known to the Jaridahans that one of the most famous and influential European scholars who became a Muslim was a Muslim. The reason is that science is not only harmful to modern Islam, but it is also useful. Dear brothers! There are people in your service who are older than you, who work less than you, and who are in charge of you, and you have five, twenty, twenty times more responsibilities. (Some banks and commercial establishments have people who earn five hundred or even a thousand rupees a month, and they go to business school for five or six years.) What is the reason for this? There are Muslims or Russians under your control who work harder than you and carry more burdens than you. What is the reason for this? Of course, you will answer that the "modern science" of those who look down on us is more than us, and the knowledge of the workers is not for us. That is the reason. We also say that your answer is correct. So, it turns out that in today's world, whether it's business or government or the arts, there's a need for modern science to get in and out of work, and everyone has a role to play. So, you, the honorable ones, wish your generation and your dear children, if you want, to develop more than you, to serve the religion and the nation. (Religion and service to 170 nations will be through science and money). You just have to be more discriminating with the help you render toward other people. Just like our compatriots sold their property for a wedding, you can sell your property if necessary, even if you try to educate your son in a modern way. What a waste of money to spend on a wedding! It will be discussed in another article as a modern teaching method. ”

The life of the Uzbek people, the works of the writer, who left a bright mark in the history of national thought, and his timeless teachings are always valuable. One of the leaders of the Jadid movement, the founder of the Uzbek theater, playwright, enlightened writer and journalist Mahmudkhoja Behbudi's dreams and hopes for freedom, independence and the future are coming true today in the new Uzbek land.

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